

Effects of ISO 9001 on Non-Financial and Financial Performance in the Organizations: A Review

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ABSTRACT: *The main purpose of this paper was to specify the impact of ISO 9001 on financial and non-financial performance. For this aim, a comprehensive literature review was carried out on the scholarly published studies, which investigated empirically the effects of ISO 9001 standard on the organization's performance in different sectors. Subsequently, the ISO 9001 studies identified and selected carefully that were relevant to the objectives and criteria of the study with the aim of achieving the results and making conclusions. The analysis of the results of the empirical studies uncovered that ISO 9001 significantly affected production process (internal business process), while this standard was not correlated with the indicators of innovation and learning perspective at significant level. Furthermore, the systematic review of the existing literature provided enough evidence that the effectiveness of ISO 9001 on customer's results and financial performance were unclear and contradictory.*

Keywords: ISO 9001 Certification; Quality Management System (QMS); Balanced Scored (BSC); Financial Performance; Non-Financial Performance; Organization's Performance.

INTRODUCTION

Nowadays, globalization and competitive pressure have generated an environment where organizations should be flexible, adaptive, responsive, and innovative [19], [21], [22]. ISO 9001 is one of the effective techniques, which can assist the companies to overcome their problems. This quality management certification belonged to QMS standards, and is a “generic standard” for all organizations, regardless of their size and field of activity. Its intention is to satisfy customers' requirements [21], [13]. Today ISO 9001 is widely adopted by different sectors in 188 countries, according to the latest ISO “survey of certifications” [7], the number of total ISO 9001-certified organizations was about 1,138,155 certificates by 2014. ISO 9001 implementation is a strategic decision [25]. Several studies were examined and determined the advantages and effects of ISO 9000 on specific performance in the organizations. Lushi et al. [13] reviewed 50 research papers concerning impact of ISO 9001 on the companies, they found that the organizations were achieved the 13 benefits of this standard, such as: “exports”, “efficiency”, “improvement in competitive position and competitive advantage”, “improvement in systematization”, “improved quality in product and service”, “improved image”, “improvements in employee results”, “improved customer satisfaction”, “improved relationships with suppliers”, “improved relationships with authorities and other stakeholders”, “market share”, “profitability”, and “sales growth”. In addition, the implementation of ISO 9001 can be the “pro-active strategy” to improve performance in different organizations [14].

Although ISO 9000 certification has shown its benefits, but the research community is still “ambiguous” to its usefulness or potential advantages of ISO 9001 in improving the overall performance of the firms [9], [17], [12]. Many studies reported that the level of the effects of ISO 9001 standard on firms' results are still unclear, contradictory and there are many “conflicting opinions” [30]. It seems that the effectiveness of ISO 9001 standard has been “contradictory” in nature indicating “positive and/or negative financial and organizational results depending on the multitude of factors studied in each particular research” [10, p. 33].

